

BRONCHITIS - IN CHILDREN AND ADULTS, SYMPTOMS, FORMS, DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT

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Abstract: *Bronchitis is a common disease of the lower respiratory tract characterized by an inflammatory process in the bronchial mucosa. The symptoms and treatment of bronchitis depend on the form of the disease: acute or chronic, as well as the stage of the disease.*

Treatment of bronchitis in all forms and stages should begin immediately and be completed: the inflammatory process in the bronchi affects not only the quality of life, but also dangerous severe complications, pneumonia, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and cardiovascular dysfunction, and causes diseases.

CAUSES OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE DISEASE

Bronchitis is often the primary infectious disease in both children and adults. The disease often develops under the influence of an infectious agent. The most common pathogens of primary bronchitis are:

Viruses: parainfluenza, influenza, adenovirus, rhinovirus, enterovirus, measles;

Bacteria (staphylococci, streptococci, hemophilic rods, respiratory forms of mycoplasma, whooping cough agent, chlamydia);

Fungi (Candida, Aspergillus).

In 85% of cases, viruses are the cause of the infection. However, in many cases, a decrease in immunity leads to the activation of pathogenic flora (staphylococci, streptococci present in the body) due to the presence of viral infections, resulting in the development of mixed floral inflammatory processes. Identification of the main and active parts of the pathogenic flora is a necessary condition for effective treatment of the disease.

Fungal bronchitis is relatively rare: the development of fungal flora in the bronchi is almost impossible with normal immunity. Fungal lesions of the bronchial mucosa are observed in significant disorders of the immune system: congenital or acquired immunodeficiency, radiation or chemotherapy, cytostatic drugs in cancer patients.

Other factors that contribute to the development of acute and chronic forms of the disease:

Outbreaks of chronic upper respiratory tract infections;

Prolonged exposure to polluted air (dust, sprays, smoke, vapors, gases), including smoking tobacco products;

Pathology of the organs of the bronchopulmonary system.

CLASSIFICATION OF BRONCHITIS

There are two main forms of the disease: acute and chronic. These two forms differ in indications, signs, symptoms, disease duration, and treatment options.

Risk factors for developing bronchitis in children include:

Premature birth;

Low birth weight;

Replacing natural breast milk with artificial supplements;

Anomalies of the broncho-pulmonary structure;

Cases of immunodeficiency;

Respiratory changes due to nasal congestion (e.g., mouth breathing);

Presence of various tumors in the nose;

Presence of foci of infection in the respiratory tract and / or oral cavity.

The acute form of the disease is very common among preschool children and accounts for 10% of all acute respiratory diseases in children, due to the unique anatomical structure of the child's respiratory system.

DIAGNOSIS OF DISEASE

Diagnosis of the disease, its causes, stage of development and the presence of complications include the following research methods:

Collection of anamnesis, analysis of patients' complaints, visual inspection, listening to breathing patterns with a stethoscope;

General blood test;

Sputum analysis;

X-ray examination to rule out or confirm pneumonia as a complication of bronchitis;

Spiro graphic examination to determine the degree of obstruction and respiratory failure;

Bronchoscopy - when anatomical developmental abnormalities, the presence of a foreign body in the bronchi, the presence of a tumor is suspected;

Instructive computed tomography.

TREATMENTS FOR DIFFERENT FORMS OF BRONCHITIS

Depending on the cause of the disease, drugs that affect the pathogen are prescribed in the first place: antiviral drugs, antibiotics, antifungals, etc.

In addition to etiologic treatment, symptomatic treatment is used: antipyretic drugs, mucolytic drugs (antitussives, acetylcysteine, and ambroxol), Broncho lytic drugs.

Both general and topical (inhalers, nasal drops) medications are used.

In addition to medication, physiotherapy, gymnastics and massage are prescribed.

In the treatment of chronic bronchitis, it is necessary to eliminate the risk factors, such as smoking, environmental exposure, occupational hazards. Once these factors are eliminated, long-term treatment with mucolytic, Broncho lytic drugs is started, and drugs that have a supportive effect on the body are prescribed. Oxygen therapy can be used in sanatoriums.

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